

IMPORTANCE OF SOYBEAN PLANT IN MEDICINE

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ABSTRACT

the article describes the role and importance of high-quality soybeans in human life in our country, the use of soybeans in the treatment of diseases such as anemia, cancer, diabetes, kidney stones, cirrhosis of the liver.

In experiments conducted at Bukhara State University, patients with iron deficiency anemia were treated with sweet cakes made from soybeans flour. Under the influence of consumption of soybeans meal 3 times a day for 10 days, the amount of hemoglobin in the blood of patients increased by an average of 20.1 g/l in 10 days, indicating that the use of foods made from soybeans flour is effective for patients with TTC.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), one in six men and one in three women in the world suffer from this form of anemia. Iron is an important trace element related to many metabolic processes, nutrient exchange, and gas exchange in the body. During the day, adults consume 20-25 mg of iron, the total reserve of this element in the body is about 4 g.

The clinical picture of anemia developed due to iron deficiency is primarily anemic and sideropenic syndrome due to impaired gas exchange in body

tissues.

Symptoms of anemic syndrome:

- General weakness, chronic fatigue;
- Weakness, inability to withstand prolonged physical and mental stress;
- Lack of attention, difficulty concentrating, rigidity;
- Getting nervous;
- Headache;
- Sometimes fainting;
- Drowsiness and sleep disorders;

- Shortness of breath, increased heart rate during physical and/or psychoemotional stress, as well as at rest;
- Black color of feces (related to bleeding in the gastrointestinal tract).

Soybeans products are recommended for the following diseases: atherosclerosis, hypertension, heart ischemia, during recovery after myocardial infarction, chronic inflammation of the gall bladder, chronic constipation, diabetes, obesity, diseases of the musculoskeletal system (arthritis, arthrosis), allergic diseases. So far, there are no restrictions on soybean products or instructions not to consume them.

Food products made from soybeanbeans help prevent cancer, heart ischemia, osteoporosis, diabetes, atherosclerosis, anemia, increase human immunity, and reduce blood cholesterol. The Food Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences recommends the consumption of soybean milk products in people with atherosclerosis, increased blood pressure, ischemic heart disease, myocardial infarction during the recovery period, chronic cholecystitis, chronic constipation, diabetes, obesity, arthritis, arthrosis, allergic diseases, stomach -recommended its use in the treatment and prevention of intestinal tract inflammation, cirrhosis of the liver, jaundice, boils and a number of other diseases.

The isoflavonoids, genestein and plant acids present in soybean prevent the onset of cancer and cardiovascular disease. Isoflavonoids stop the formation of cancerous tissue, genestein stops the growth of tumors in the initial period, phytic acids slow down the growth of tumors that have appeared.

There are five known anti-cancer agents in soybeans products, one of which is phytoestrogens (isoflavones), which are anti-cancer agents unique to soybean foods. Scientists have concluded that genistein's antioxidant properties and anti-proliferative properties are the main reasons for its anti-cancer effects. Soybeans isoflavones have clear therapeutic effects on breast cancer, colon cancer, lung cancer, prostate cancer, skin cancer, and leukemia. Soybeans isoflavones also help prevent ovarian cancer, colon cancer, stomach cancer, and prostate cancer.

Functions and Benefits of Soybeans Extract with Soybean Isoflavones:

1. Natural soybeans extract prevents cancer, inhibits tumor, reduces the risk of cancer.
2. Soybeans extract powder lowers cholesterol, reduces the possibility of heart attacks, prevents and treats cardiovascular diseases.
3. Soybeans extract powder relieves menopause syndrome in women and prevents osteoporosis.
4. Natural soybeans extract protects the human body from free radical damage, improves the immune system.
5. Soybeans extract can nourish the stomach and spleen and protect the nervous system.
6. Soybeans extract powder reduces the thickness of cholesterol in the human body, prevents and treats cardiovascular diseases.

Application of Soybean Extract with Soybean Isoflavone:

1. In the food industry, soybeans extract is added to beverages, liquids and foods as functional food additives and raw materials.

2. Soybeans extract is widely added to various health products to prevent chronic diseases or alleviate the symptoms of climacteric syndrome.
3. Soybeans extract is widely used as a raw material in cosmetics with the function of delaying skin aging and tightening, so it makes the skin very smooth and delicate.
4. Soybeans extract soybean isoflavone can be used in pharmaceutical field.

Soybean foods prevent diabetes, kidney stones, and liver disease. According to doctors, 10-15 percent of adults will experience an unpleasant disease such as kidney stones in their lifetime. The risk increases especially in people aged 40 to 60 years. In addition, patients who already have kidney stones are 50 percent more likely to develop a new one. One of the main reasons for the formation of kidney stones is the lack of water in the body. Water helps dilute the concentration of these substances in the urine, which then harden and turn into stones. Therefore, it is important to observe the balance of moisture and drink in the hot season.

Another important factor to control is the amount of salt. A diet high in sodium increases calcium in the urine, which combines with oxalate or phosphorus to form kidney stones. Even excess animal protein increases the risk of kidney stones because it increases the amount of uric acid in the body, which can also form kidney stones.

Cirrhosis of the liver is a chronic disease of the liver; in which liver tissue becomes inflamed and part of it is replaced by connective tissue. Acute inflammation of the liver - in hepatitis, its B, C, D forms, when acute hepatitis turns into chronic hepatitis, in infectious diseases such as malaria, tuberculosis, wounds, brucellosis, chronic inflammation of the gall bladder and biliary tract, in regular poisoning by various chemicals, as well as in alcoholism and other appears for reasons. Cirrhosis of the liver is a slowly developing chronic disease. Cirrhosis of the liver manifests itself in different ways and depends on the form and period of the disease; despite the fact that the liver is hardened and dysfunctional during examination, a person can walk for a long time without noticing any symptoms of the disease. When the disease worsens, the patient becomes debilitated, loses weight, loses appetite, stutters, feels nauseous, sometimes vomits, has diarrhea or constipation, stomach rests, body temperature rises, as a result of accumulation of fluid in the abdomen (disease), nosebleeds, body itching, sometimes turns yellow; anemia peaks; the liver and especially the spleen become enlarged and hardened.

Cirrhosis of the liver is treated for a long time, when the disease worsens, the patient should be hospitalized immediately. Strict adherence to diet is important. The patient is mainly given dairy and vegetable foods that are easy to digest, rich in sugar, protein and vitamins (especially vitamin C and group B). You can eat cottage cheese (which has easily digestible proteins), lean meat, fish, as well as cream or sour cream with a little butter; drinking alcohol is strictly prohibited. Medications are prescribed to prevent the progression of liver cirrhosis. In the treatment of cirrhosis of the liver, it is important to eliminate the factors that cause it. If an infection leading to cirrhosis of the liver is detected, measures are taken to eliminate it. In order to prevent cirrhosis of the liver, it is necessary to improve working and living conditions, fight against alcoholism.

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